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SHORT COMMUNICATION

The first record of *Illinoia liriodendri* (Monell, 1879) (Hemiptera, Aphididae) from Ukraine

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Abstract

Illinoia liriodendri is reported for the first time in Ukraine as a new invasive species of aphids. It was found feeding on *Liriodendron tulipifera* at the 'Olexandria' State Dendrological Park of the NAS of Ukraine in June 2024.

Keywords: *Illinoia liriodendri*, *Liriodendron tulipifera*, phytophagous insects invasion, aphid

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One of the undesirable consequences of plant introduction is the spontaneous distribution of phytophagous insects trophically related to introduced species into new habitats. However, appear of feed-related species of insects sometimes is separated in time from the plant species introduction. Such an example is the introduction of the tulip tree (*Liriodendron tulipifera* L., Magnoliaceae) to Europe from North America in the late 19th century. The tulip leaf aphid, *Illinoia liriodendri* (Monell, 1879) that feeds on *L. tulipifera* did not appear in Europe until the 1990s. Initially, an invasion of this North American species was recorded in France, and then it has spread to many European countries, including Germany, Italy, Slovenia, United Kingdom, Portugal, Croatia, Slovakia, Polska, Serbia, Hungary, Spain (Bozsik, 2012; Bella, 2014; Franjević et al., 2015; Kollár & Barta, 2016; Kanturski et al., 2017; Petrović-Obradović et al., 2018; Meseguer et al., 2024). This aphid species has not been recorded in Ukraine until yet.

Recently (June 6, 2024), we observed *I. liriodendri* feeding on top and undersides of tulip tree leaves and producing many honeydew in the arboretum 'Olexandria' (Bila Tserkva, Kyiv region, Ukraine). The colony consisted of larvae, apterus, and alatae viviparous females. Hence, here we report it with provided illustrations (Fig. 1).

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Figure 1. *Illinoia liriodendri* in the arboretum 'Olexandria' (Bila Tserkva, Kyiv region, Ukraine): **A** – the colony on the underside of tulip tree leaf; **B** – the aptera viviparous female; **C** – the alata female; **D** – cauda and siphunculi of the aptera viviparous female; **E** – head of the alata viviparous female.

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Перше повідомлення про знахідку *Illinoia lirioidendri* (Monell, 1879) (Hemiptera, Aphididae) в Україні

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Уперше повідомляється про виявлення в Україні інвазійного виду попелиць *Illinoia lirioidendri*, який було зареєстровано в червні 2024 року в Державному дендрологічному парку “Олександрія” НАН України на дереві *Liriodendron tulipifera*.

Ключові слова: *Illinoia lirioidendri*, *Liriodendron tulipifera*, інвазія комах-фітофагів, попелиці